

Effects of Cement Stabilization on Geotechnical Properties of Expansive Soil Derived from Ameki Formation in Ozuitem, Near Bende, Southeastern Nigeria.

Ezeala, H. I., Okeke, O.C., Amadi, C.C., Irefin, M.O., Obini, N.

Department of Geology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

Corresponding author's email: ezealahenryi@gmail.com

Abstract

The majority of engineering issues in Ozuitem (Isiegbu) stem from construction engineers' negligence in assessing and mitigating the impact of expansive soils on engineering structures. Cement stabilization is a very important soil improvement technique which serves as solution to expansive soil (clay) on engineering structures by bringing important modifications/stability to their engineering properties before it can be considered a good foundation/subgrade material for construction of light weight structures. This study aims at analyzing the effects of using cement as additives for improving the geotechnical properties of expansive soil derived from Ameki Formation in Ozuitem (Isiegbu) near Bende Southeastern Nigeria, so as to reduce their swelling potentials and inversely increase its strength characteristics. The study examined the untreated geotechnical properties of expansive soil sampled from Ozuitem (Isiegbu) representing Ameki Formation, cement was introduced at 2%, 4%, 6%, 8% and 10% respectively serving as a stabilizing agent. Geotechnical tests were repeated after cement was added to determine the effects of using cement additive on cohesive soils of Ameki formation and we achieved an optimal soil-cement stabilization at 8% cement addition revealing liquid limit (51.90% - 35.50%), plasticity index (24.60% - 5.00%), linear shrinkage (14.00% - 7.20%), Maximum dry density (1.52Mg/m³ - 1.75Mg/m³), unsoaked CBR (10.04% - 25.10%) and soaked CBR (4.60% - 23.44%) conforming with federal ministry of works and housing specifications for roads and bridges. Results obtained showed significant reduction on its swelling potentials (LL, PI & LS) and increasing strength characteristics on CBR and MDD (strength potentials) of the soil.

Keywords: Ameki Formation, cement additive, geotechnical properties, Ozuitem, expansive soils, stabilization

1.0: Introduction

Geologists and construction engineers consider the mechanical properties of soil like strength, stiffness and permeability as an important component of the soil for all developmental works which should be considered before embarking on any type of construction work due to the complexities faced with constituent materials of soils especially when engineering structures are founded on an expansive soil.

Ameki Formation outcropping in Ozuitem (Isiegbu) near Bende is composed of sandy shale, clayey sandstone, fossiliferous shale and finegrained argillaceous sandstone with thin limestone band (Reyment, 1965; Arua, 1986). Its dark grayish silty clay (expansive soil) is an abundant constituent of earth materials used for engineering construction purposes, serving as foundation soil for buildings or subgrade for road pavement construction in the study area.

Geotechnical investigations carried out in the study area classified them as CH soils known to be inorganic fat clay. Due to its weakness, light weight engineering structures constructed in the area has experienced series of engineering defects with variations in moisture content of the foundation/subgrade soils leading to a shrink and swell behaviour causing visible cracks and potholes on road pavement and differential settlement on buildings. The effects of these expansive soils on engineering structures has lead to total destruction, losses of life and properties accounting to trillions of Naira in the area which has necessitated the need for stabilization with cement to help mitigate and analyze the effects of using cement additives before use and rehabilitation needs by construction engineers thereby, ensuring durability.

According to Ogbuchukwu and Okeke, (2021); they examined the use of cement and lime as soil stabilization additives and it was observed as an effective technique of modifying problematic/expansive soils by improving its geotechnical behaviour because it had a general effects of reducing the swelling indicators (liquid limits, plasticity index and linear shrinkage) by reducing the tendency of expansive soil to swell in the presence of water. Cement soil stabilization is aimed at improving the geotechnical properties of expansive soils by controlling the shrink and swell behavior of the soil, improving the load bearing capacity, strength and durability of subgrade to support road pavement and foundation for building structures (Powrie, 1997; Okeke et al., 2015 and Kalu et al., 2024).

Cement stabilization technique has been practiced over the years and can be of used on any kind of soil except soils that contain organic matter and other compounds like sulphur (Ogbuchukwu and Okeke, 2021). Clay with high plasticity can be stabilized with small amount of cement up to 2% added to modify the geotechnical behaviour of the soil but added in larger quantities when substantial changes are required (Bell, 2007). Cement stabilization agent used in the treatment process of expansive soils acts in such a way that when mechanically mixed to attain a homogenous mixture with a natural soil, it helps to reinforce the bonds between the grains and particles or filling the pore spaces thereby reducing void ratio, increasing soil cohesion and maintaining soil moisture content by serving as water proofing agent (Afrin, 2017).

Stabilization of problematic soils with cement can be achieved through hydration process then followed by flocculation and crystallization of the hydrated products thus known as hydraulic grip (Larsson et al., 2009 and Ogbucgukwu and Okeke, 2021). It is a complex process with series of unknown chemical reactions which can be affected by presence of impurities, water-cement ratio and curing temperature (MacLaren and White, 2003). Therefore, the curing time varies due to the presence of these factors on crystallization and

gain in strength of stabilized soil and should be appropriately taken note of during mix so as to achieve the desired strength required for a certain engineering structure.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effects of using cement as additives for improving the shear strength of expansive soil derived from Ameki Formation in Ozuitem (Isiegbu) near Bende Southeastern Nigeria, by increasing its resistance to softening when in contact with water through hydraulic grip which serves as a water proofing agent to soil particles (Sherwood, 1993). The expansive soil samples collected were mixed with cement at 2%, 4%, 6%, 8% and 10%, tested at different curing times for seven (7) days to investigate the effects of cement on the engineering properties of expansive subgrade soil.

Fig 1: Failed section of Uzuakoli - Ozuitem highway caused by Ameki FM

2.0 Description of study area

2.1 Physiography and climate of study area

The study area KM 8 Uzuakoli – Ozuitem (Isiegbu) highway is located in the tropical rainforest zone of the Niger Delta basin Southeastern Nigerian Sedimentary complex of present-day Abia State (Fig 2). It lies between latitude 5°28' N to 5°40' N and longitude 7°26' E to 7°43' E and elevation of 129m above sea level. The area experiences alternate climate between rainy and dry seasons, high temperature levels between 20°C to 30°C, high relative humidity of about 76° and dense evergreen vegetation (Nigerian Metrological Agency, 2007).

The topography features rugged cuestas composed of sandstone and plateau escarpments with steep slopes in the north, while gentle hills and valleys in the south composed of silty clay. The area is drained by several water bodies, including the River Igwu, Ase River, River Idonyi, Kaw ibo River, Okwanka stream, Ikwu River, and Inyong River, forming a dendritic drainage pattern with tributaries joining the collector stream at right angles. The study area is structurally controlled and expressed as rectilinear channel geometry (Nwajide, 2013).

Fig 2: Location map of the study area.

2.2 Geology of the study area

The study area falls within the Niger Delta Basin of Southeastern Nigeria, geographically situated in the Gulf of Guinea which is located between latitudes 3° and 6°N and longitudes 5° and 8°E (Nwajide, 2013). Stratigraphically, southeastern Nigeria sedimentary basins are composed of three (3) sedimentary episodes (Short and Stäuble, 1967; Murat, 1972; Obi et al., 2001). The three (3) episodes are: (1) Abakaliki-Benue episode (Aptian-Santonian), (2) Anambra-Benin episode (Campanian- Early Palaeocene), and (3) Niger Delta episode (late Paleocene-Pliocene). The succession of Niger Delta basin encountered in the study area includes coastal plain sands of Benin formation, Ogwashi-Asaba formation, Bende – Ameki formation and Imo formation.

According to Okeke and Igboanua, (2003); Ezeigwe, (2005); Nwajide, (1992) Ameki formation is a lateral equivalent Nnaka Sands, they were laid in the early - middle Eocene (Reyment, 1965; Berggren, 1960; Adegoke, 1969). The lithology of the study area as shown in Table 1 is composed of Benin formation which consists of unconsolidated fine-medium-coarse grained, cross-bedded sands occasionally pebbly with localized clays and shales, Ogwashi-Asaba formation consisting of variable succession of clays, sands and with seams of lignite, Bende-Ameki formation (Ameki Group) consist of alternating sandy shale, clayey sandstone, fossiliferous shale (consisting of molluscs, foraminifera, and corals), and finegrained argillaceous sandstone with thin limestone bands while Imo formation is composed of fossiliferous limestones, marls and blue-grey shales with sand lenses (Reyment, 1965).

Fig 3: Geologic map of southeastern Nigeria showing the Paleogene formations (adopted from Ekwenye et al., 2020)

Fig 4: Geologic map of the study area (adopted from Chiaghanam et al, 2017)

Table 1 below illustrates the regional stratigraphic sequence of soils derived in Bende (Niger Delta Basin) area.

Table 1: Stratigraphic sequence of Niger Delta and Anambra Basin (Modified from Nwajide, 2005).

Age	Basin	Stratigraphic Units						
Oligocene-Recent	Niger Delta	Ogwashi-Asaba Fm						
Eocene		Ameke/Nanka Fm/Nsugbe Sandstone (Ameke Group)						
Thanetian		Imo Formation						
Danian	Anambra Basin	Nsukka Formation						
Maastrichtian		Ajali Formation						
		Mamu Formation						
Campanian		Nkporo Fm	Nkporo Shale	Enugu Fm	Owelli Ss	Afikpo Ss	Otobi Ss	Lafia Ss

3.0 Materials and methods

3.1 Sample collection

Expansive soil samples used to perform this study were collected from Ameki Formation in Umuahia Bende Area with a spade at a depth of 2m in two (2) different study locations (Ubani and Isiegbu) with the aid of a geologic map, global positioning system (GPS), polythene bag, masking tape and ink maker. The process of sample collection followed strictly specified standards proposed by British Standard Institution (BSI) 1377 (1990), US Bureau of Reclamation (USBR) (1963) and Spangler and Handy (1973).

3.2 Laboratory tests

Soil samples collected from the study area was later taken to Geological Laboratory Federal University of Technology Owerri for a detailed Geotechnical investigation on the expansive soil samples to help identify the geotechnical index parameters of the soil in accordance to BS 1377 (1990) and Singh, (2004) which includes Atterberg limits (LL & PI), optimum moisture content (OMC), linear shrinkage (LS), compaction and California bearing ratio (CBR).

In accordance to the methods proposed by Ingles and Metcalf, (1972); Peck et al., (1974); Nelson and Miller, (1992), dry weight of the soil samples were mixed with various percentages of cement of about 2%, 4%, 6%, 8% and 10% and cured for 7 days then another set of Geotechnical investigation was carried out to observe the effect of adding cement on the geotechnical properties of expansive soils collected from Isiegbu (Ozitem).

4.0 Results and discussion

4.1 Results

Table 2 below represents results obtained from the geotechnical index parameters and strength characteristics of expansive subgrade soils sampled from two (2) different locations at zero percent (0%) and effects of cement additive on engineering properties of the studied soils at 2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10% derived from Ameki Formation in Isiegbu (Ozitem) Area.

Table 2: Chemical stabilization with cement on engineering properties of expansive soils derived from Ameki Formation in Ozitem Area.

% Cement Added	LL (%)	PL (%)	PI (%)	LS	MDD (Mg/m ³)	OMC (%)	Unsoaked CBR (%)	Soaked CBR (%)
0	51.90	27.30	24.60	14.00	1.56	12.80	10.04	4.60
2	47.75	30.35	17.40	11.30	1.60	11.13	14.10	9.79
4	43.35	30.90	12.45	10.50	1.63	8.00	18.22	14.91
6	40.85	31.25	9.60	9.10	1.71	5.40	22.10	18.02
8	35.50	30.50	5.00	7.20	1.75	3.95	25.10	23.44
10	37.95	30.80	7.50	6.90	1.58	3.75	30.15	17.50
FMWH (1997)	< 36	-	< 12	< 8	< 1.76	-	> 40	> 15

Fig 5: Variation of liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL) and plasticity index (PI) of expansive soils from Isiegbu with different percentages of cement

Fig 6: Variation of linear shrinkage of expansive soils of Isiegbu with different percentages of cement

Fig 7: Variation of maximum dry density (MDD) of expansive soils of Isiegbu with different percentages of cement

Fig 8: Variation of optimum moisture content (OMC) of expansive soils of Isiegbu with different percentages of cement

Fig 9: Variation of CBR (soaked and unsoaked) of expansive soils of Isiegbu with different percentages of cement

4.2: Discussion

The use of cement as stabilizing agent for cohesive soils (clay) has been extensively practiced by construction engineers and researchers. Engineering properties of stabilized soil derived from Ozuitem area presented in table 2 above is very important in determining the effectiveness and improvement of problematic soils. Table 2 indicated a general effect of reducing the tendency of the soil to swell and as well increasing its strength characteristics as can be deduced as follows:

The liquid limit (51.90% - 35.50%), plasticity index (24.60% - 5.00%), linear shrinkage (14.00% - 7.20%) and optimum moisture content (12.80% - 3.95%) values showed a reduction trend that aligned with FMWH, (2007) specification for workability of expansive soils while plastic limit (27.30% - 30.50%), Maximum dry density (1.52Mg/m³ - 1.75Mg/m³), unsoaked CBR (10.04% - 25.10%) and soaked CBR (4.60% - 23.44%) values showed an increasing trend with increase in the stabilizing content indicating an improved strength characteristics of the cohesive soil (Ezeh et al., 2017).

4.2.1: Effects of cement on subgrade samples

The use of cement in soil stabilization of expansive subgrade for construction of road pavement becomes effective when it lowers the plasticity of the soil particles thus making it moisture insensitive by creating an agglomeration structure of calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) and calcium hydroxide (CaOH) which bounds surrounding particles.

Table 3 shows the rate of reduction (% reduction) the geotechnical index parameters (LL, PI, LS) of soil samples from Isiegbu (Ozuitem) area when treated with various percentages of cement while Table 4 shows the rate of increase (% increase) in strenght of California bearing ratio (CBR) and maximum dry density (MDD) of the soil when treated with various percentages of cement.

A rapid reduction of swelling potentials and critical degree of expansion of the subgrade soil was observed on addition of 2% of cement to 7.99% (51.90 – 47.75) on LL, 29.26% (24.60 – 17.40) on PI and 19.28% (14.00 – 11.30) on LS. A reduction percentage was observed in

optimal addition of 8% of cement to 31.59% (51.90 – 35.50%) on LL, 79.67% (24.60 – 5.00%) on PI and 48.57% (14.00 – 7.20%) on LS respectively.

An increase in durability and strength characteristics of subgrade soil was observed on addition of 2% of cement to 35.57% (10.40 – 14.10%) on Unsoaked CBR, 112.82% (4.60 – 9.79%) on soaked CBR and 2.56% (1.56 – 1.60) on MDD whereas a maximum increase percentage was observed in optimal addition of 8% of cement to 141.34% (10.40 – 25.10%) on unsoaked CBR, 409.56% (4.60 – 23.44%) on soaked CBR and 12.17% (1.56 – 1.75%) on MDD respectively.

Table 3: Evaluation of effectiveness of cement additive on geotechnical index properties cohesive subgrade samples from Isiegbu.

% of cement added	LL (%)	% Reduction	PI %	% Reduction	LS %	% Reduction
0	51.90	-	24.60	-	14.00	-
2	47.75	7.99	17.40	29.26	11.30	19.28
4	43.35	16.47	12.45	49.39	10.50	25.00
6	40.85	21.29	9.60	60.97	9.10	35.00
8	35.50	31.59	5.00	79.67	7.20	48.57
10	37.95	26.87	7.50	69.51	6.90	50.71

Table 4: Evaluation of effectiveness of cement additive on CBR and MDD of expansive subgrade samples from Isiegbu.

% of cement added	Unsoaked CBR (%)	% Increase	Soaked CBR (%)	% Increase	MDD (Mg/m ³)	% Increase
0	10.40	-	4.60	-	1.56	-
2	14.10	35.57	9.79	112.82	1.60	2.56
4	18.22	75.19	14.91	224.13	1.63	4.48
6	22.10	112.50	18.02	291.73	1.71	9.61
8	25.10	141.34	23.44	409.56	1.75	12.17
10	30.15	189.90	17.50	280.43	1.58	1.28

Clay is considered an abundant soil worldwide which plays a very important role in various aspect of construction works and earth systems but due the mineral composition of most clays, they exhibits a shrink behaviour when NOT in contact with water and a swell

behaviour when in contact with water which has made it very complex and difficult to manage by construction engineers. Soil stabilization with cement therefore causes a reduction in the degree of expansion or compressive stresses and swelling potentials of cohesive soils by improving its shear strength and durability.

Soil stabilization with cement can be achieved when a saturated soil of certain particle size distribution is mixed with cement to form Cement-stabilized base through a process known as hydration process which grows into crystals that can interlock with one another giving a high compressive strength (Afrin, 2017). When the soil is mixed with cement and water, the calcium silicate and calcium aluminates present in the cement reacts with the compound in the soil cement to form a cementitious compound of calcium-silicate-hydrates (C-S-H) and calcium-aluminate-hydrate (C-A-H), releasing enough calcium hydroxide (CaOH) (Prusinski and Bhattacharja,1999; Rajasekaran, 2005).

Hydration process is a chemical reaction that takes place when water is added to a soil mixed with cement to form a cementitious gel after compaction which fills the void between the soil particle leading to a reduction in the void ratio of cohesive subgrade soil thus, growing into crystals that acts like a hydraulic grip which has the ability to interlock with one another overtime. Cement hydration reaction is not dependent on minerals present in the soil however, the water available in the soil is a responsible factor for the reaction to take place which results to the agglomeration of C-S-H and Ca(OH)₂ that decreases the swelling potentials and increases the strength of the material but it will not change the structure of soil (EuroSoilStab, 2002).

Fig 10: Bonding process between cement particles and sand particles after (Firoozi et al., 2017)

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) when mixed with water (hydrous state), hydration occurs forming cementing compounds of calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H), calcium-aluminate-hydrate (C-A-H) and excess calcium hydroxide (CaOH) is released at approximately 31% by weight. The two major constituent which has important effect on the strength characteristics of soil cement are tricalcium silicate C₃S (Ca₃SiO₅) and dicalcium silicate C₂S (Ca₂SiO₄), they have adhesive and cohesive properties which is capable of binding together mineral fragments in presence of water so as to produce a continuous compact mass (Al-Tabbaa and Perera, 2006; Makusa, 2012; Jha and Sinha, 2009 and Gupta and Gupta 2004; Firoozi et al., 2017).

During hydration process, C3S, and C2S will carry out a complex hydration reaction to form calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) and calcium silicate hydrate (3CaO·2SiO₂·4H₂O, (C–S–H) gel (Kazemian et al., 2017). The growth and agglomeration of these cement hydration products altogether not only form their own special structure but also fastened (fixed or binded) the sand/stone/steel bar in the structure. These shapes, as well as the numbers of such crystals in the cement paste, have an important impact on the mechanical strength of the soil (Yuan and Ji, 2009).

Conclusively, Ordinary Portland cement stabilization mechanism adopted two popular theories namely; the crystalline theory by Le Chatelier (1919) and gel theory proposed by Taylor (1971) which have been integrated into a combined gel/crystalline theory which ensures associated weak base exchange reaction.

Expansive soil stabilized with cement does not swell when exposed to water; it is considered an effective way that improves the quality of subgrade materials by improving the workability, load-bearing characteristics, stability and soil impermeability. Typically, treating unpaved roads composed of fine grain soils with cement is prohibitively expensive but proved to be more economical in granular and aggregate soils due to its cementitious materials and calcium hydroxide (CaOH) formed during stabilization process (Little, 2000) and tend to gain more strength faster compared to when lime is used due to its hydration action.

During the study, the maximum dry density (MDD) observed an increasing trend which indicates an increase in the degree of compactness of the subgrade soil while optimum moisture content (OMC), liquid limit (LL), plasticity index (PI) and linear shrinkage (LS) all observed a reduction trend when cement additives are introduced indicating a decrease in swelling potential, degree of expansion and permeability falling within the proposed Federal Ministry of Works and Housing, (1997) standards/specifications for road pavement subgrade and foundation soils for light weight building construction.

Cement stabilization results from the studied samples of Ameki formation proved that when soils are treated with up to 8% cement, it significantly reduces the swelling potential and degree of expansion conforming with Holtz and Gibbs, (1956) & Ola, (1981) experimental findings; increase in strength characteristics of the soils also at 8% of cement associated to linear shrinkage informing about the non-critical degree of expansion of cohesive soils obtained from Ameki formation (Attimeyer, 1956) and this is the reason behind the gain in strength characteristics of MDD and CBR. The results attained a fixation point at 8%; further addition of cement will not have any effect on the geotechnical behavior of the soil because it has reached a saturation point.

5.0: Conclusion

Soil samples derived from Ameki formation in Isiegbu Ozuitem area of Abia State where studied and confirmed “expansive soil” due to its affinity to water and inability to conform with FMWH, (1997) specifications as good subgrade for road pavement construction. Results

from this study analyzed the effect of adding different percentages of cement which evidently reduced its tendency to swell using Atterberg limit test (LL & PI) as reference and degree of expansion using linear shrinkage test as reference. An increase in the strength characteristics of the expansive soil was also noticed when the soil cement was compared with the natural soil using MDD and CBR as a reference point too.

Stabilization of expansive Ameki formation revealed that it can act as a good foundation and subgrade soil when treated with cement through hydration, flocculation and agglomeration of C-S-H and CaOH between the pore spaces of soil particles. Cement is preferably used on silty clay with low plasticity but very expansive to manage due to expensive nature of cement in the market and spatial nature of the soil to be treated while lime is most preferred because it can be used to treat soils with high liquid limit, high plasticity index and it provides better resistance to moisture ingress.

The sole aim of soil treatment is strength gain through plasticity reduction which increases the workability of the soil, reduction in moisture content and increased durability. Environmental factors like carbonation and sulphate attack from the top layer are some of the challenges faced with soil stabilization which is the reason why we allowed curing for 7 days.

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